

INTEGRATING RECYCLED FIBREBOARD FINES IN THE SURFACE LAYER OF PARTICLEBOARD

Particleboard (PB) is a wood-based panel (WBP) with a three-layer structure. Its coarse-particle core assures internal strength, bending resistance, and reduced weight, while very fine-particles (fines) guarantee smooth panel surfaces. PB is manufactured by combining wood chips and fines with glue and compressing the mixture under heat. By adjusting the glue formulation, pressing conditions and additives, boards can be made with different properties including moisture resistance or fire retardancy, making them cost-effective and versatile.

APPLICATIONS

Given its structure, PB is ideal for laminating and painting and widely used in cabinets, shelves, tables, wall panels, partitions, doors, decorative elements and flooring. Decorative PB can be finished with paper foil, veneers, and laminates making it suitable for both residential and commercial environments.

ACHIEVEMENTS

EcoReFibre Project Demonstration:

PB with recycled fines achieve comparable performance as reference panels.

INTEGRATING RECYCLED MDF FINES IN THE SURFACE LAYER OF PB

Fines can be obtained from wood processing and from recycling fibreboards (FB) i.e. another type of panel consisting mainly of wood fibres. Indeed, when recycling FB, the panels are disintegrated into a mixture of fibres and fines, with their relative proportion depending on the process used. In the EcoReFibre project demonstration, these fines were integrated at 10%, 20% and 30% into the surface layer of PB to test if they can substitute the standard wood mix. The fines were produced with the “dry process” developed by Dieffenbacher – a water and chemical-free mechanical process. At lab scale, substitution of up to 30% with FB fines showed promising results. However, to ensure product performance and process stability, the industrial trial focused on 20% substitution with FB fines integrated into the conventional production line.

Panel made with 0% recycled fines
(100% virgin sawdust)

Panel made with 20% recycled fines

FUTURE CHALLENGE

Visual surface quality proved sensitive to material variability with occasional defects at higher substitution levels caused by local fines agglomeration. Analysis showed that these agglomerates were linked to storage in big bags and mechanical conveying methods that did not sufficiently disperse fines clusters. Future work should therefore focus on improved feedstock preparation and handling to achieve a more homogeneous surface layer and fully exploit the potential of recycled fines under industrial conditions.

CIRCULARITY

As a renewable, bio-based and carbon storing material wood is a key driver for Europe’s circular bioeconomy. Reintegrating post-consumer WBPs into production helps close material loops and extend the lifespan of wood. Through horizontal recycling of WBPs, material value is maintained and the dependence on virgin wood is reduced.

An innovative waste sorting line and smart recycling technologies enable end-of-life WBPs to be broken down into fibres and particles which are then reintegrated into new panel production. Industrial trials have shown that PB can integrate up to 20% recycled fines in their surface layer, while achieving performance similar to reference panels. From an economic perspective, increasing recycling can help broaden the raw material base, improve the availability of scarce raw materials, and support stabilising volatile virgin wood prices. Of course, also investments in recycling equipment and process adaption are required for industrial-scale production.

By fostering a circular value chain, from waste sorting to panel manufacturing, the EcoReFibre project contributes to the objectives of the Green Deal, in particular the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR), and supports the goals of the Circular Economy Action Plan (CEAP), while aligning with the upcoming Circular Economy Act (CEA).

IMPACT

As part of its circular bioeconomy efforts, Sonae Arauco already uses around 30% recycled wood in its total wood input, mainly in particleboard production, where recycled content can reach beyond 70%. Within EcoReFibre, the company focuses on increasing the share of recycled wood and addresses the technological challenges of incorporating recycled fibres and particles into new panels, and other products across its portfolio.

KEY PRINCIPLES OF CIRCULAR BIOECONOMY INCLUDE:

- Designing products that minimise waste
- Multi-actor dialogue
- Improving resource and energy efficiency
- Using by-products and secondary raw materials
- Promoting awareness and social engagement

ECOREFIBRE CLOSES THE MATERIAL LOOP THROUGH:

- New and adapted technologies & methods
- New collaborations
- New and adapted infrastructure
- Lifecycle analysis
- Supportive regulations and standards
- New business models

CONTACT

SONAE ARAUCO

Portugal | Spain | Germany | South Africa

Adelaide Alves

Group R&D Director

aalves@sonaearauco.com

Sonae Arauco on LinkedIn

sonaearauco.com

EcoReFibre on LinkedIn

SLU SWEDISH UNIVERSITY OF AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

Uppsala, Sweden

Stergios Adamopoulos

Professor, Wood Science

stergios.adamopoulos@slu.se

SLU on LinkedIn

slu.se

ecorefibre.eu

PARTNERS

Photo credits: Sonae Arauco, InnovaWood. Layout: Fovéa création.

This document reflects the authors' views only and neither the Agency nor the Commission are responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

**Funded by
the European Union**